

Hope, A. (2020). Figuring out Benjamin's 'angel of history': 'Reading', *Angelus Novus* and sublime metaphor. *Textual Practice*, 34(6), 995–1020.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/0950236X.2019.1586755>

Cover Page

Author name: Alexander Hope

Affiliation: Universidad Autónoma de Madrid

Email: alexander.hope@uam.es /

Postal Address:

Dr Alexander Hope,

Departamento de Filología Inglesa,

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid,

Facultad de Filosofía y Letras,

Campus de Cantoblanco,

28049 Madrid

España

Figuring out Benjamin's 'Angel of History': 'reading',

***Angelus Novus* and Sublime Metaphor**

Abstract

The image of the 'Angel of History' forms the centrepiece of one of Walter Benjamin's most famous essays: 'On the Concept of History'. This text has a troubled exegetical history, with numerous competing interpretations attempting to explain what Benjamin really meant. Few, with the exceptions of Timothy Bahti and Sigrid Weigel, have stopped to examine the fragments' rhetorical structure or to ask what it is about 'On the Concept of History' that leads to such a proliferation of readings. This essay, rather than searching Benjamin's corpus for the ciphers to decode the fragments' meaning, instead focuses on the complex rhetorical structure of 'the angel of history'. It argues that an interplay between grammar and rhetoric induces a multiplication of possible interpretations, and indeed that this poetic density seems to involve an imperative to 'translate', both the 'original' (German or French) text and its complex relationship with the 'derived' English version, both interlinguistically and intralinguistically, as Roman Jakobson (1959) would say. It shows that this complex rhetorical structure actually performs the argument put forward in the fragments about the impossibility of historicist totalising readings of history, yet in its injunction to translate or interpret, 'bear witness to the unrepresentable' (Lyotard), seems to ask that very impossible over and over again.

If we no longer take for granted that a literary text can be reduced to a finite meaning, but see the act of reading as an endless process in which truth and falsehood are intrinsically intertwined then the prevailing schemes used in literary history [...] are no longer applicable.

Paul de Man, Blindness and Insight, ix

The difficulty of allegory is rather that this emphatic clarity of representation does not stand in the service of something that can be represented.

Paul de Man, Aesthetic Ideology, 51

The translator is indebted, he appears to himself as translator in a situation of debt; and his task is to render, to render that which must have been given.

Jacques Derrida, Des Tours de Babel, 200

Introduction: many interpretations, few readings

Paul de Man was fond of suggesting that the texts of greatest rhetorical difficulty were those most frequently interpreted ‘philosophically’, with scant regard to their literary refinement.¹

While de Man himself addressed himself to the ‘The Task of the Translator’,² he did not analyze Benjamin’s last and arguably most enigmatic piece, ‘On the Concept of History’ (OCH). That de Man, or indeed Derrida, that other great ‘Archie De-bunker’ as de Man describes the author of ‘White Mythology’,³ did not apply themselves to the intertwined textual, aesthetic and political problems occasioned by OCH is perhaps no great surprise.

While both were prolific, to (largely) neglect one text in the history of philosophy is not in itself remarkable.⁴ What, however, is truly remarkable is how a text, OCH – that seems to be

about the limits of representation and the political consequences of assuming the ability to see the ‘true picture’ of history – can give rise to so many different interpretations which implicitly or explicitly claim to be the ‘true’ meaning of what Benjamin meant. This tendency seems to occur whether the critic follows a Marxist-materialist or a theological/Judaic mysticism line – corresponding roughly to the positions taken by the principal guardians of Benjamin’s legacy, Theodore Adorno and Gershom Scholem. (Marc de Wilde provides a useful round up; see also Kia Lindroos’s chapter).⁵ This also occurs with ‘incompatible’ readings of Benjamin’s oeuvre or those that – as do both Michael Löwy⁶ and Stephané Symons⁷ – argue Benjamin reformulates both classical Marxism and Jewish theological mysticism to produce a ‘fourth’ position which is not assimilable to either, nor reducible to a simplistic dialectic. With regard to the ninth fragment, the ‘Angel of History’, it garners more attention from scholars with an interest in angels such as Suzanne Hobson, Michael Serres, Angela Moorjani and Paul Coillili.⁸ For those whose research interests are angel-focused the lack of detailed critical and rhetorical engagement is understandable, for those interested in history, allegory or the dialectical image, less so. As Timothy Bahti suggested in 1979 of the authors of *Materialien zu Benjamins Thesen ‘Über den Begriff der Geschichte’*, ‘while there is no scarcity of scholarly reference [...] there is all too little reference to the material density and complexity, to the *rhetoric* Benjamin’s theses’⁹; aside from Bahti, the most rhetorically astute reading comes from Sigrid Weigel, who is one of the few to notice the shifts in viewpoint throughout the fragment.¹⁰ Alison Ross has also rather scathingly observed: ‘In general, the tone of Benjamin scholarship is one that avoids critical engagement with his writing and instead treats it in a posture of religious exegesis’.¹¹ Oddly, while Ross herself notes the importance of Klee’s *Angelus Novus* for Benjamin’s thought, fragment IX gets little mention in her analysis of the dialectical image. The problem of the linguistico-rhetorical and aesthetic difficulty of ONC is usually sidestepped in favour of searching Benjamin’s wider

Textual Practice

corpus for keys to *decode* the text ('scholarly reference'), whether these codes are to be found in the *Arcades Project*, the Agesilaus Santander essay,¹² the Karl Krauss essay¹³, the Theologico-political Fragment¹⁴ or in the Palimpomena to OCH. As Ross implies, there seems to be a quest to *unveil* its 'sacred' yet politically secular meaning, as a quasi-religious text but with little reference to its rhetoric.¹⁵ Scouring Benjamin's corpus to understand his thinking is clearly useful, however this decoding too often seems used as a lightning rod to jump away from confronting its 'material density'. This article will focus on these questions of rhetoric and reading in relation to OCH. However, the inclination to decode and give a definitive gloss of OCH's quasi-sacred meaning shall never be far away; it cannot be a coincidence that so many of the near uncountable interpretations take similar forms but differing meanings.

The interpretation of 'On the Concept of History' has in general been dominated by a particular set of hermeneutic procedures. On the rare occasions that the rhetorical or grammatical – or indeed aesthetic – functioning of the text are discussed, the theory tends to focus on Benjamin's own theory of language or allegory¹⁶ or on the dialectical image.¹⁷ Esther Leslie, in one of her books on Benjamin, quotes the ninth 'vignette', as she describes it, in its entirety and then gives a nice gloss of the apparent meaning of the fragment, as if it says what it says. She then tells of a 1962 Theodore Adorno radio interview in which 'Adorno insists that Klee's angel is the angel of the machine'.¹⁸ The association with mechanization is both interesting and well-founded; however, figuring out what the fragment is saying and how it relates to the Klee painting (or does not) is taken as largely obvious. Leslie's interpretation is well thought out, but as do many others, she jumps away from the text itself to interpret it through a prism borrowed from another reference – reference as cipher rather than supplement, referring in rather than figuring out.

There is much excellent scholarship involved in these decodings and interpretations but many could not be called 'readings' in Paul de Man's sense.¹⁹ Michael Löwy's *Fire Alarm* is an admirable piece of scholarship, but not consistently 'reading' in the sense given by de Man or Andrej Warminkski. To cite Rodolphe Gaché's introduction to Warminkski's de Man-inflected *Readings in Interpretation*:

Contrary to interpretation, which represents an operation of decision making in a totalizing perspective, *reading* is the reading of the text's unreadability, that is, of its structural incapacity to lend itself to unequivocal and unproblematic totalizations.²⁰

For Gaché's, some reading is always necessary for any interpretation, but 'reading' aims to show the openness of the text, while 'interpretation' tends towards totalization. This citation shows the danger of quoting 'out of context' in that it reduces Gaché's elaboration of the interplay between reading and interpretation to a slogan, Warminski's title is after all *Readings in Interpretation*. (We could perhaps think of a cline, like Barthes's 'readerly' and 'writerly'.²¹)

This distinction can be illustrated with reference to Löwy's analysis of fragment IX in *Fire Alarm*:

The thesis *presents itself* as the commentary on a painting by Paul Klee [...]. In *reality*, what it describes bears very little relation to the painting: what is involved here is, in the main, the projection of his own feelings on to [*sic*] the German artist's subtle and austere picture. [My italics]²²

Herman Rapaport, in his review of Löwy's book, praises his scholarship but upbraids the lack of engagement with OCH's relation to Klee's *Angelus Novus*.²³ Löwy's suggestions of intertextual relations with Baudelaire's *Fleurs du Mal*, Schiller and Hegel are genuinely

Textual Practice

interesting; however, there is little to justify his exclusion of Klee ‘in *reality*’.²⁴ This is ‘interpretation’ in the sense given by Gasché; by producing a separation between appearance, ‘presents itself’, and ‘reality’, Löwy gives himself licence to tell us what Benjamin’s feelings and intent were, ‘it is an allegory in that its elements have no signification outside the role intentionally assigned to them by the author’.²⁵ Readers of Derrida’s ‘Signature, Event, Context’ will recognise the ‘communication’ metaphor in this presentation of what Benjamin ostensibly meant.²⁶ This gesture significantly simplifies ‘interpretation’, since it makes the subject of the analysis Benjamin’s intent, which is carried through the text to the reader, what linguists call the ‘conduit metaphor’²⁷ – instead of how the text *performs* in relation to Klee and its own complex history. Derrida’s reading of Austin demonstrates, through iteration and *différance*, the illegitimacy of intent as a guarantor. By excluding Klee from a fragment that begins, ‘There is a picture by Klee called *Angelus Novus*. [...] This is how the angel of history must look’,²⁸ Löwy robs the text of one of its principal rhetorical devices and reduces the possible scope for *reading* (however, both Bahti and Weigel also largely exclude Klee).

OCH is doubtless an overdetermined text, as Rapaport notes, ‘there does seem to be a lack of agreement on how to read [the fragments]’.²⁹ I would argue that OCH is little read and frequently interpreted. Alison Ross gives an excellent account of how this lack of agreement has played out in Benjamin scholarship as regards the dialectical image. She berates Pierre Missac for failing to explain *how* this image might work and for viewing Benjamin’s methodology as ‘intentionally oxymoronic’, ‘under the guise of faithfulness to Benjamin’s suggestive formulations’; Rolf Tiedemann is upbraided for assuming continuity between the concept of truth in *Trauerpsiel* and history as citation in the *Arcades* ‘as if these were self-evidently continuous’; the final Benjaminist to be admonished is Susan Buck-Morss for making Benjamin’s selection of historical material appear arbitrary, and then attempting to

account for arbitrariness through its political concern.³⁰ Ross also approvingly reports Buck-Morss's insistence that the meaning of the work cannot be up to 'capriciousness of the reader'.³¹ Indeed, to take this position is merely to abdicate responsibility for reading. Unfortunately, Ross's focus remains on the *Arcades* and she has little to say about the enigmatic images in OCH. However, much of what she argues for Benjamin scholarship seems to go for OCH. In particular, continuity between earlier works and OCH is often assumed rather than demonstrated, perhaps beginning with Scholem's 'Walter Benjamin and his angel'.³²

Returning to the slippery question of reading, de Man at times seems to make 'interpretation,' as the inevitable failure to do justice to the text, seem at some points necessary or at least inevitable, and 'reading' impossible. De Man offers the suggestion that the hermeneutic operation of attempting to determine meaning and the stylistic or poetic question of *how* something means are in fact not complementary.³³ Perhaps basing himself more on de Man's praxis, Warminski argues:

not only does literary reading (and writing) always come before the text of the interpretation (*Auslegung, Erläuterung*) as its condition of possibility, but it also always goes after the text of the interpretation as its condition of impossibility.³⁴

For Warminski 'literary reading' is both the condition for interpretation and that which shows that the *telos* of mastery implied is essentially impossible, as Gasché elaborates 'literary reading [...] is thus reading which, by being faithful to the play of relations that forms the in-between space of dyadic textual items [and which] demonstrates the impossibility of reading in the sense of interpreting'.³⁵ This is not a naïve belief in the accessibility of some sort of 'Ur-text' outside the history of interpretations rather a sort of excessive faithfulness to the

text and, as Derrida makes clear, this is an injunction that comes from the work not the author.³⁶

Allegories of Reading, Reading Allegories

Warminski borrows heavily from de Man, who did not systematize ‘reading’ and ‘interpretation’ quite as strongly. In his reading of Blanchot in a chapter of *Blindness and Insight* and the comments on ‘reading’ in *Allegories of Reading*, however, de Man’s comments on figurality enter into a fruitful ‘dyadic’ relationship with Warminski. For de Man allegory or figure makes totalizing interpretation impossible.³⁷ As noted by Löwy and many others, OCH has been frequently analysed in terms of allegory, and this was one of the ways Benjamin characterized his own method.³⁸ De Man credits Benjamin with ‘[helping] to restore [allegory] to some of its full implications’.³⁹

Following de Man’s approach, however, rather than start with allegory, we will begin with questions of ‘grammar and rhetoric’. To clarify the distinction between reading and interpretation, I cite fragment IX for reference:

There is a picture by Klee called *Angelus Novus*. It shows an angel who seems about to move away from something he stares at. His eyes are wide, his mouth is open, his wings are spread. This is how the angel of history must look (*muß so aussehen*). His face is turned toward the past. Where a chain of events (*Kette von Begebenheiten*) appears before *us*, *he* sees one single catastrophe, which keeps piling wreckage upon wreckage (*Trümmer auf Trümmer*) and hurls it at his feet. The angel would like to stay, awaken the dead, and make whole what has been smashed.⁴⁰ But a storm is blowing from Paradise and has got caught in his wings; it is so strong that the angel

can no longer close them. This storm drives him irresistibly into the future, to which his back is turned, while the pile of debris (*Trümmerhaufen*) before him grows toward the sky. What we call progress is *this* storm.⁴¹

Robert S. Lehman in an article entitled ‘Allegories of Rending’ cites Benjamin’s *Arcades Project*, ‘I needn’t say anything. Merely show’ and then goes on to claim that ‘the ninth thesis is surprisingly clear’.⁴² Lehman then makes an interesting point on IX, ‘though we may be told what the angel knows, we cannot see what the angel sees’, which as we will see later is part of the fragment’s complex formation of shifting viewpoints; however, rather than interrogate the text through his chosen critical prism, temporality and Benjamin’s allegory, Lehman veers off through an erudite analysis of the *Trauerspiel*, Kant’s ‘intellectual intuition’ and a mediation on baroque allegory yet touches only briefly on how this allegory might actually work in OCH. As a further example, Kia Lindroos writes of the metaphor of ‘*Angelus Novus*’, cites an interesting comparison with *Zentralpark* to elucidate progress as ‘already given (*jeweils gegebene*)’ but does not analyze how Benjamin ‘uses’ metaphor.⁴³ Here perhaps we have the critical reception in a nutshell: the fragment seems to encourage interpretation but the plurality of responses suggests that these scholarly interpretations are radically incomplete – even in an article on time and allegory there is much scholarly reference and little, though at least some, attention to rhetoric.

‘And as the task is impossible at the approaches to the sacred text that assigns it to you, the infinite guilt absolves you immediately’, as Derrida says of *Genesis* in *Des Tours de Babel*, his essay on ‘The Task of the Translator’;⁴⁴ however, in the case of OCH there seems to be a disregard for the impossibility of this demand, and this demand – according to Derrida’s reading of Benjamin – comes not from the author but from the work, ‘the *formal* law in the

Textual Practice

immanence of the original text'.⁴⁵ Clearly, we are not far away from questions of translation as the translation cited here is from the German, but Benjamin also wrote a French 'version' or translation, included in *Écrits Français*.⁴⁶ In de Man's piece on 'The Task of the Translator' he notes that to write on this most famous of Benjamin's texts is something of a rite-of-passage for theorists.⁴⁷ This other overdetermined text from Benjamin, and especially Derrida's reading of it in *Des Tours de Babel* have relevance here as much for the questions of reading and intention as for those relating to the disputed translation of OCH.⁴⁸ There does appear to be 'a structure of injunction that comes from the work', a demand to translate 'reading between the lines' as if OCH were – like the example in *Des Tours de Babel* – a kind of sacred text.⁴⁹ However, Benjamin was not God, nor did he claim to be; thus, the guilt of being inadequate to the text is not infinite, and – like Lyotard's reworking of the sublime⁵⁰ – the text does not absolve us of attempting to think the 'tiger's leap' into the past, nor the impossibility of the angel's view while we aid the 'sur-vival' of the text.⁵¹ This injunction appears to operate as much intralinguistically as interlinguistically, following Roman Jakobson's schema.⁵² Drastically abbreviating Derrida's treatment of Benjamin's metaphor of the fruit and skin as the relation between text and translation in the 'The Task of the Translator', we can say that the English translation and French version are now part of the 'sur-vival' of the text, and the promise of the 'infinite rebirth of languages'.⁵³ Reading OCH closely in translation is evidently problematic, and I will make reference to both the German and French, but the value given to the text, its 'sur-vival', is in part due to Harry Zohn's idiosyncratic translation in *Illuminations*.⁵⁴ As Derrida clarifies: 'if the original calls for a complement, it is because at the origin, it was not there without fail, full, complete, total'.⁵⁵ The language of OCH in English has undoubtedly 'grown' that language. The question would then become *how* the 'structure of the injunction' appears in the fragment and *how* it

continues to generate such a wealth of exegetical material, both inter- and intralinguistically; what is it that seems to both demand and resist attempts at mastery?

We are already in too much of a hurry. The passage begins by insisting that Klee's *Angelus Novus* is 'how the angel of history must look'. 'Grammatically' as de Man would say,⁵⁶ the passage insists that it 'shows' the appearance, *aussehen*, of the angel of history.⁵⁷ It says 'grammatically' that there *is* an angel of history, via an existential presupposition, and that Klee's painting is how it 'must' look, and therefore that the passage itself is a description of Klee's depiction of this angel. 'Surprisingly clear', indeed (and this without considering Weigel's identification of three different angels).⁵⁸ As Bahti notes, many critics of OCH attempt to catalogue the differences between Benjamin's description and Klee's painting. The critics in the *Materialien zu Benjamins Thesen* – the review of which occasioned Bahti's article – who 'enter into thematic disputes over the difference between Klee's picture and Benjamin's' are, however, not 'missing the essential point' as Bahti claims.⁵⁹ On a grammatical level, the text insists that it merely 'shows' Klee's painting, which is then contrasted to the Klee painting it says it is.

Bahti's argument is that the image of the Klee painting is a false lure, because Benjamin's text creates an image that is *not* a representation of *Angelus Novus*, 'there *is* no Klee painting, but rather only a single Benjaminian structure – a verbal emblem *inscribing* its "visual" component or image'.⁶⁰ He argues that the supposed referent (as construed grammatically by the text) of IX is not really a referent, that it is not 'really' a description of Klee's painting at all, that the text is 'rhetorical' in the same sense as a so-called 'rhetorical question'. Bahti insists on reading 'rhetorically' – as figural in a more or less traditional sense (Weigel also

Textual Practice

argues that the painting and textual image are separate, as an ‘as if’, emphasizing the subjunctive).⁶¹ For Bahti, Klee’s painting becomes part of a ‘single Benjaminian structure’ in order to produce an ‘ironic allegory’ where Scholem’s lines that precede the ‘main’ text work together like an emblem, picture and *subscriptio*. Bahti’s reading is very sophisticated, but by beginning with rhetoric and excluding grammar it loses a layer that is essential for how the text functions as ‘mutually determining’ – between not just the ‘verbal image’ induced by the passage and the lines that precede it, but between both the textual/verbal image, *subscriptio* and Klee’s painting, as a ‘constellation’.⁶² He argues IX belongs to the traditional (allegorical) genre of an ‘Emblem’: ‘an emblem involves a picture (picture) followed by a title or motto (*inscriptio*) followed in turn by a “caption” (*subscriptio*)’.⁶³ The lines from Scholem’s ‘Greetings from the Angelus’, also occasioned by *Angelus Novus*, function as *inscriptio* before the presentation of the ‘description’ of Klee’s painting – akin to the caption or *subscriptio*. However, this shows merely one recursive rhetorical or figural structure, but, like Löwy and Weigel, largely excludes Klee’s painting.

In *Allegories of Reading* de Man laments that semiologists have forgotten the distinction between grammar and rhetoric. He also claims that the symbiotic relation between them is sufficiently difficult that a ‘concise theoretical exposition [is] beyond my powers’.⁶⁴ We must therefore infer the principles from de Man’s ‘pragmatic’ examples. The first of these is Archie Bunker replying ‘what’s the difference?’ to an inquiry about lacing bowling shoes over or under, which engenders an alternative ‘rhetorical’ reading which means ‘I don’t give a damn what the difference is’.⁶⁵ This, clearly, is akin to Bahti berating the critics who read too literally in searching for differences between Benjamin’s description and the painting that ostensibly occasions it; Bahti reads the fragment as if it were a rhetorical question, as if the figural meaning *denied* the literal. Remarking that a figural meaning can always be treated

literally (or grammatically), de Man makes a subtle shift, via Derrida and Nietzsche, in his definition of rhetoric:

The grammatical model of the question becomes rhetorical not when we have, on the one hand, a literal meaning and on the other hand a figural meaning, but when it is impossible to decide by grammatical or other linguistic devices which of the two meanings (that can be entirely incompatible) prevails. Rhetoric radically suspends logic and opens up vertiginous possibilities of referential aberration.⁶⁶

Rhetoric for de Man is not simply another name for figural language, but rather the production of undecidability, potentially 'literal' and 'figural' in which it is impossible to decide their 'proper' meaning without reference to something outside the text. For this reason, it would be unsurprising to de Man to read Löwy claim 'for the others [allegorical meanings in IX] we have to find their social and political meaning by reference to other writings of Benjamin's'.⁶⁷ Despite its poetic density, the rhetorical possibilities and referential aberrations are hardly touched upon.

As de Man's reading of the Yeats line 'How can we know the dancer from the dance?' demonstrates, it is not necessarily the case that the literal meaning is naïve and the figural more sophisticated. In taking IX at its word and reading the text as genuinely a description of *Angelus Novus*, we are forced to consider not just the textual/verbal image (and indeed the 'mutually determining' relationship with the Scholem lines identified by Bahti) provided in OCH but also how Klee's 'childlike and uncertain signifier'⁶⁸ – as Geoffrey Hartman somewhat unkindly describes the painting from 1920 – might be considered the 'angel of history'. Grammatically, the text offers *Angelus Novus* as a referent, but the painting does resolve the tension between readings but rather is forces another reading of the painting that

Textual Practice

may or may not align with the ‘textual image’. As de Man shows, grammar and rhetoric are not opposed (although potential meanings may be) but does not obviate the need to ask ‘what’s the difference?’ Thus, if we are to read IX ‘rhetorically’, it becomes undecidable whether ‘in reality’ the ninth thesis is a description of Klee’s *Angelus Novus* or whether ‘in reality’ it is a self-contained projection of Benjamin’s imagistic thought that links only contingently to *Angelus Novus* through the invocation of its proper name. (The second is Weigel’s position, arguing for three separate angels and largely excluding the possibilities of overlap; importantly, she also highlights that to read the image-constellation as metaphorical in the classical sense, as substitution or transference, freezes what is clearly a dynamic image).⁶⁹ In short, the undecidability of the rhetorical structure produces ‘vertiginous possibilities in referential aberration’ because we are unsure whether to read the description as a description pretending to be of or ‘in reality’ of Klee’s painting. Furthermore, as highlighted by both Andrew Benjamin and Weigel, OCH should be read as a ‘constellation’,⁷⁰ in which case the act of deciding whether there are three angels or one has its own rhetorical effect – as well as in tension with the other fragments that form the co-text.

Returning to *Allegories of Reading*, de Man demonstrates that a key passage in *Swann’s Way* which metafiguratively valorizes metaphor is dependent on metonymy. He calls the undecidability produced by rhetorical questions (like ‘what’s the difference?’) the ‘rhetorization of grammar’, and these latter effects in Proust where what is ostensibly figural – Marcel/the narrator praises value of metaphor but in doing so is reliant on metonymic structures – ‘the grammatization of rhetoric’, which then potentially produces a sort of negative truth (in Proust, the demystification of the power of reading). As Hartman adduces in a chapter on de Man, however, this negative truth can still be undone by irony, which comes from ‘outside’ the system, and OCH is clearly an ‘ironic allegory’.⁷¹ So, to what extent

can we identify rhetorization of grammar and/or grammatization of rhetoric in OCH? Is there a disjunction between what is ostensibly presented by the narrative, and the way in which it is presented, as with Proust? How might this affect the possibility of historical representation, be it historiography or historical materialism, as it figures out in the ‘angel of history’?

Allegories of Reading, Reading Allegories

Löwy argues that Thesis IX is based on a Baudelairian allegory ‘between the sacred and profane, between theology and politics, which runs through each of the images’.⁷² There undoubtedly is an interplay between sacred – or better said, theological – and profane, between celestial vision and human that organises the rhetorical structure of the passage, but Löwy’s assertion that ‘the profane counterpart to the storm blowing from a Paradise is Progress’ is too simple because it ignores the rhetorical complexity of the text, and indeed allegory. As Bainard Cowan explains in an important essay on Benjamin’s theory of allegory, for Benjamin ‘allegory is pre-eminently a form of experience’ but this experience – contrary to the Romantics – is from a world of signs, pre-empting Derrida’s grammatology.⁷³ Cowan shows that in Benjamin’s theory of allegory, ‘experience’ and ‘expression’ become allegorical, pointing now to ‘collective entities such as rhetoric and tradition rather than the self “proper”’.⁷⁴ This would accord with de Man, who cites Benjamin defining ‘allegory as a void “that signifies precisely the non-being of what it represents”’.⁷⁵ As de Man insists, ‘Allegories are always allegories of metaphor and, as such, they are always allegories of the impossibility of reading – a sentence in which the genitive “of” has itself to be “read” as a metaphor.’⁷⁶ Note that de Man makes a ‘grammatical’ structure like the genitive into a metaphor; the impossibility of ‘reading’ is so precisely because of a metaphor that constitutes the concept ‘of’ reading, the ostensible movement of coming out of implied by the genitive is itself a metaphor, a ‘figuring out’, inducing – as Derrida would insist – a catachrestic

Textual Practice

structure where all metaphor is non-true metaphor because the return to the sensible always turns out to be another metaphor, effaced or not.⁷⁷

It has been argued that for de Man history and reading are almost the same thing, but we should not get too far ahead of ourselves with OCH.⁷⁸ The concise exposition of the alignments between Benjamin and de Man's theories of allegory falls beyond my powers, save to note that both point to a certain incompleteness, an inability to read history that I would argue is played out by the complex textual scene of the angel of history. In an essay on Pascal, de Man helpfully suggests that 'allegory (as sequential narration) is the trope of irony (as the one is the trope of zero)'.⁷⁹ We will return to this question of allegory in the close analysis of fragment IX. (Perhaps though the Benjamin of OCH is rather more optimistic than de Man about possible exceptions to this situation with the 'the genuine historical image as it briefly flashes up' (VII) suggesting a possible true *picture* of the past.⁸⁰ A picture made more complex by the insistence, grammatically, that *Angelus Novus* is how the angel of history 'must appear' / *muß so ausssehen* / 'devra être l'aspect que presente.')⁸¹

Let us refocus on rhetorical matters. IX appears in the context, or co-text, of the critique of historicism and its 'homogeneous empty time' and as the 'focal point', as Löwy says, of OCH.⁸² As such its projection of multiple temporalities onto what may be either, as Bahti and Weigel both suggest, a Benjaminian textual image (rhetorically) or Klee's picture (grammatically) would inflect the reading of the other fragments. We can see the construction of an allegorical structure where the placing of the angel in a spatial tableau works to project a number of distinct and potentially incompatible temporalities. 'There is a picture [...] This is how the angel of history must look. [...] His face is turned towards the past [...] this storm drives him irresistibly into the future'. What Bahti calls a 'verbal image'

borrowing the conventional Western metaphorical conception of time as a linear movement or ‘progression’ (past to future in a line, *pax* the eternal return) to place and orient the Klee/Benjamin image in such a way as to show the naiveté of this conception – the orientation of Klee’s painting is horizontal in contrast to the linearity of time. However, the placement of the angel is arguably metonymic, relying on contiguity, there is no ‘truth’ in the sense of comparing Achilles to a lion, as de Man articulates the difference between metaphor and metonymy, rather it is more akin to taking Mr Ford for a motor car (metonymy).⁸³ The intermediate status of immortal angels between mortal humans and eternal God makes this metonymic placement plausible (what cognitive linguists call the ‘mapping scope’). This metonymic schema is refined further by specifying the angel’s orientation ‘face [...] towards the past’ – the angel is *trans*-fixed; that is to say, held ‘irresistibly’ by the storm but continuing to move with linear time; that is to say, the text uses metonymic structures to place the angel in the commonly conceived folk metaphor of linear time as progression.

This linear metaphor of time is then disrupted by the antithetical parallel between ‘a chain of events appears before *us*, *he* sees one single catastrophe’, where the implicit linear metaphor is contrasted with the ‘*Trümmer auf Trümmer*’, ‘wreckage upon wreckage’ – strengthened in German by the preposition ‘*vor*’ appearing in ‘before [*vor*] *us*’ and ‘at [*vor*] his feet’.⁸⁴ (To my knowledge, Weigel is the only commentator to note the series of oppositions and ‘changes in perspective’ in the fragment).⁸⁵ The antithetical relation with the chain metaphor of events, which passively ‘appear’ to us, to the angel’s ‘he sees’ induces a contrast in perspectives, the narrowness and binding of the chain with the much greater scale of the angel’s ‘one single catastrophe’, linear vs. a tableau; the greater information provided by the clauses relating to the ‘catastrophe’ serving to further emphasise the great scope of the angel’s vision versus that of the chain before us (perhaps also echoing IV, ‘that sun which is

Textual Practice

rising in the sky of history’).⁸⁶ This chain ‘before us’, in an co-textual relationship with the critique of historicism would then be *aligned* with the view of the angel, both facing the past, as the antithesis implies – but one is narrow and binds, the other (the angel) sees all at once, without sequence: the *maintenance* of a simultaneity. (Weigel emphasizes the collapse of a gap between past and present in the dialectical image, akin to the view of the angel). By the same token – and possibly relating to A, where the, presumably historical materialist, historian ‘ceases to tell the sequence of events like the beads of a rosary (*Rosenkranz*)’⁸⁷ – it can be argued that the text constructs a metaphorical analogy between seeing ‘events’ and the links of a chain (*Kette*, also shackles or necklace), binding, enslaving *us* both to and with this narrow and restricted view of history.

In the ‘Paralipomena’ to OCH, unfinished notes to an unfinished text,⁸⁸ Benjamin states that:

The multiplicity of histories resembles the multiplicity of languages. Universal history in the present day sense can never be more than a kind of Esperanto. The idea of universal history is a messianic idea. [...] only in the messianic realm does universal history exist.⁸⁹

Benjamin shows the limits and limiting of an ‘artificial’ present day universal history, which akin to Esperanto would have no *genuine* history. The narrowness of the chains that bind can then be read as a figural performance of historicism’s empty universal history, contrasted as narrowly binding together a chain of events (cf. the ‘lineage’ and document ‘transmitted from one hand to another’ of VII as well as the ‘rosary’⁹⁰). Note that the interrelation, or constellation, of metaphors is dependent on their contiguous, metonymic, placement in the image schema. Additionally, we can associate the angel’s view as the presentation of this ‘messianic’ universal history, a genuine messianic universal history – in view, if not in

messianic potential to induce 'Judgement Day', since the angel 'would like to stay' but cannot because of the 'storm blowing from Paradise'. This distinction between a genuine (messianic) universal history and the limited view accorded to *us* is performed by the rhetorical structure, the recourse to the Paralipomena supports this interpretative gesture, but OCH had already provided the image-construct through an interplay between metonymic placement and conventional metaphor.

Figures of the sublime, sublime figures

This antithetical relation of 'chain of events' and 'one single catastrophe' also has a multiplying effect that recalls the Kantian sublime; interestingly, the sublime is mentioned in both de Man and Derrida's pieces on 'The Task of the Translator' but is seldom, if ever, mentioned in relation to OCH. The sublime is most fully developed in Kant's third *Critique*, following a section on determinate form and the beautiful. '[T]he sublime [...] is to be found in a formless object insofar as limitlessness is represented in it [...] the beautiful seems to be taken as the presentation of an indeterminate concept of the understanding, but the sublime [...] of reason.'⁹¹ The sublime is that which is almost too large for presentation, an aesthetic judgement of reason, but one which highlights our inability to fully comprehend what is being presented. The sublime marks the extension of aesthetic -prehension, grasping, where as much is lost at one end as is gained at the other, while apprehension may grasp the almost-too-large for presentation 'it can go on to infinity', it comes at the extent of comprehension, which 'soon reaches its maximum'.⁹²

Returning to OCH and focusing on the allegorical presentation of time, we can see that there is a shift from a secular notion of time as forward movement/linear to a theological one, 'the angel would like to stay [...] But a storm is blowing from Paradise'. This in de Man's terms

Textual Practice

should be considered ambiguous rather than undecidable, since a traditional metaphor of time is left implicit in the first few lines, ‘seems about to move away [...] face is turned toward the past’; so, while a secular temporal localization could be assumed from ‘toward the past’, it is not clear if this is cognate with the storm or not (the last line with the ‘storm we *call*...’ perhaps suggests the latter). The storm is, initially, theological or even eschatological, coming from ‘Paradise’ and driving the angel ‘into the future, to which his back is turned’, again working antithetically with the first lines that emphasize the angel looking at the past as a kind of messianic universal history.

The line ‘wreckage upon wreckage and hurls it at his feet’ potentially marks the scale of the angel: these ‘ruins’, ‘fragments’, ‘pieces’ – as Bahti prefers the translation of ‘*Trümmer*’ –⁹³ are of the entirety of history and are thrown at the angel’s feet, yet he sees all of history at once. Without introducing a different way of ‘seeing’ in which all of those events are somehow translucent yet seen by the angel, the obvious conclusion is that the angel must have a higher viewpoint than amidst the wreckage, and since the wreckage lands in front of (*vor*) the angel’s feet, or he must be more massive than the level of the wreckage.⁹⁴ As Klee’s painting lacks scalar reference, it allows for such a multiplication of scales both grammatically and figurally, nor is this a problem if *Angelus Novus* is taken as only contingently, metonymically connected to the angel of history by its proper name. The text uses aesthetic judgement to contrast our limited perspective, ‘appears before *us*’, with that of the angel: where *we* see only linear connections of, *the angel* sees a vast tableau; the chain metaphor introduces a sensory quantum that can then be multiplied to produce a contrast with the greater capacities of the angel, akin to the mathematical sublime. Precisely by expressing history as it appears to ‘us’ as a limited chain it enables a suprahuman, suprasensible messianic *idea*, in the Platonic sense, of a (messianic, in *scope* if not capacity, given the

angel's impotence) universal history beyond human 'comprehension'. In short, it produces something akin to the Kantian sublime by requiring the intervention of the imagination to compensate for the failure of the presentation to remain equal to the concept presented.

This is an allegorical technique, as Cowan explains, for Benjamin, '[t]he affirmation of the *existence* of truth, then, is the first precondition for allegory; the second is the recognition of its *absence*'.⁹⁵ This, with the 'non-being of what it represents', shows how the metaphorical construction of the chain is yoked metonymically through antithesis to the tableau of the angel's greater vision. As Cowan adumbrates, 'the truth *is* the form. Representation is thus not to be viewed for its end product but for its process'.⁹⁶ The allegorical play then does not produce positive knowledge but rather a 'negative truth', as de Man says, by representing the entirety of history as 'one single catastrophe' (downturn) which exists only as a messianic idea that can only be 'apprehended'. OCH, therefore, puts forward the impossibility of *any* human historians representing true universal history to themselves through the very form of representation.

In part at least, this negative truth uses the allegorical play between the 'sacred' and the 'theological' to produce a sort of multiplying Kantian sublime. As with Kant's version of the sublime, IX sets up a sensory quantum that can perhaps be 'comprehended'; Klee's image initially appears to have a determinate form. In the mathematical sublime, this sensory quantum is erected as a measure that can be multiplied in order to 'apprehend' forms too colossal to be presented, 'almost too large for presentation' as Derrida puts it.⁹⁷ The sublime figure of the angel is, then, not merely rhetorical ornament to be interpreted but something which performs the failure of historicist universal history. It is the performance of the failure

Textual Practice

to present universal history today through the very failure of representation that represents it; this is the negative truth of allegory. It can be understood as meta-rhetorical, commenting on the possibilities of presenting a messianic universal history, albeit negatively. The multiple levels of the allegory, and the different constellations which the recursive relationships produce, are indicative of the many fragmentary ‘histories’ that Michel de Certeau,⁹⁸ would go on to identify some 30 years later in language reminiscent of the Paralipomena.⁹⁹

The rhetorico-aesthetic sublime of OCH is important because it *performs*, in the Austinian sense, precisely this inevitable fragmentation of representation in relation to the ‘colossal’¹⁰⁰ of history in its entirety. In *The Truth in Painting* Derrida analyses this ‘colossal’ of the third *Critique*; ‘the colossal’ is that which is ‘almost too large’ for apprehension and for presentation, ‘almost unrepresentable’.¹⁰¹ It is that which allows us to ‘catch sight’ of ‘something which is not a thing, since it is a concept’.¹⁰² It is, Derrida insists, the mark of a concept that is ‘almost too large for any presentation’.¹⁰³ Benjamin’s ‘angel of history’ performs and indeed *demonstrates* rhetorically the too large for *faithful* presentation of history in its entirety and sets this against the historical materialist’s ‘that image of the past which unexpectedly appears [...] in a moment of danger’ of the co-text.¹⁰⁴ To clarify this rhetorically-induced sublime, we will draw on Derrida’s interpretation:

It [the sublime] smashes to smithereens [*Il fait voler en éclats*: makes it fly off into pieces] the signifier which would presume to measure itself against infinity. More precisely, form, the act of forming (*Gestalten*), is destroyed through what it expresses, explains or interprets. [...] this sublime inadequation must be thought on the basis of the more and not the less, the signified infinity and not the signifying finitude.¹⁰⁵

This bears a remarkable resemblance to the enormity of Benjamin’s *Trümmerhaufen* in the

ninth thesis. Through sublime allegory, a genuinely messianic vision of universal history is presented, but only to apprehension. In this sense the ‘*Trümmer*’ can be seen as metafigural, since it explains what the trope itself does by attempting to measure up to the ‘signified infinity’.¹⁰⁶ However, this unity should not be taken as something that can be unified; the vision of the angel is fragmented, and the grammatical beginning of IX gives us Klee’s *Angelus Novus* – a painting in which we see a ‘new angel’ looking back at us, and nothing of the angel’s messianic view.

Further evidence can be provided for this rhetorical sublime by XVIII. It evokes the Kantian mathematical sublime in a similar way to IX. Mathematical reason is needed in order to grasp ‘the paltry fifty-millennia history of homo sapiens’ being reduced to ‘two seconds at the close of a 24 hour day’ in ‘relation to the history of [...] life on earth’¹⁰⁷; evidently, it is the scale of the difference which presents problems for our ‘comprehension’ as it is ‘almost too large’ for presentation.¹⁰⁸ In the same fragment we can see a parallel figure for the aesthetico-rhetorical compression required to present the angel’s view of history as the maintenance of a simultaneity:

Now-time, which, as a model of messianic time, comprises the entire history of mankind in a tremendous abbreviation, coincides exactly with the figure which the history of mankind describes in the universe.¹⁰⁹

In this passage, we can see that the figure produced by the mathematical sublime, with the two seconds at the end of a 24 hour day, is already pre-figured by the angel’s sublime vista of the entirety of history at once. However, there are reasons not to associate ‘now-time’ with the time of the angel’s view, though the chain of linear time should certainly be opposed to ‘now-time’. This ‘now-time’ seems closer to ‘the true image of the past flits by’ (V), and

Textual Practice

‘Historical materialism wishes to hold fast that image of the past which unexpectedly appears to the historical subject in a moment of danger’, than the angel’s sublime vision of an eidetic messianic universal history. Read in conjunction with XVIII, then, the angel’s vision, as potentially *of* ‘messianic time’, would be that which the historical materialist attempts to reproduce in miniature ‘a model’, inverting the escalating scales of IX. Peter Fenves, in one of the best recent books on Benjamin, argues of this passage that:

The “enormous abbreviation” that characterizes “now-time” derives from the shape of time: every segment of time, no matter how small, is like all of time; the smaller the segment, the more “enormously” does its recapitulative character appear. The appearance makes the “now” of time—which is to say, its shape—recognizable. In order for historiography to correspond with time without succumbing to myth, the philologist cum historian must abstain from attributing to the “historical process” the essential characteristic of time: continuity.¹¹⁰

In Fenves’s elaboration, now-time as a model is a form of synecdoche in relation to messianic time, it reflects the whole that it is ‘blasted’ out of (discontinuity). ‘Continuity’ can be attributed to the chain metaphor, where linking events is clearly seen as a form of binding, and how does one escape from chains? By breaking them. However, much as I am a fan of Fenves’s careful study of Benjamin’s early work, care is required in attributing such a specific interpretation of the monad to ONC. Fenves argues that a particular mathematical curve which would probably have been known to Scholem was the model for the monad – now-time – messianic-time relation put forward in OCH. The mirroring of the entire universe in the Leibnizian monad, whilst each monad remains unique,¹¹¹ certainly does offer a combination that fits with the ‘messianic arrest of happening’ in XVII and the ‘model of messianic time’ in XVIII. In contrast to the Leibnizian harmony that the monad implies, however, ONC is replete with the language of violence, ‘blast’, ‘fragments’, ‘the present as

now-time *shot through with splinters of messianic time*',¹¹² and repeated assertions of a specific relation between a present and a specific past. This suggests that while now-time can be seen as a sort of monadological synecdoche in relation to messianic time, there is significant tension in this 'constellation', and a very careful reading of Leibniz in relation to this structure would be warranted. Furthermore, it could be argued that the version of the mathematical sublime in 'two seconds at the close of a 24 hour day' in XVIII reinforces the problem of representing time and history that runs throughout OCH, emphasizing fragmentation rather than unity. Clearly, the interpretation of Benjamin's messianic, or merely how the messianic appears in OCH, is a subject which itself is replete with commentaries.¹¹³ There is evidently a semantic association between the angel and messianic time in terms of the traditional hierarchical chain of being (metaphor). While the angel's vision as now-time cannot be definitively excluded, its association with humans and the historian in XVIII and A suggest messianic time as more likely.

This would also be a 'dynamic' sublime, since this sublime, Kant informs us, is related to 'an aesthetic judgement as a power that has no dominion over us' in which 'power' (*Macht*) is defined as 'a capacity which is superior to great obstacles. The same thing is called *dominion* if it is also superior to the *resistance* of something that itself possesses power'.¹¹⁴ The storm is therefore a form of dynamic sublime. There is an escalating scale of might, from ourselves caught up in the debris, to the angel, to the storm – which might be messianic time or that which blows across messianic time on the scale of the angel – with messianic time beyond the scope of aesthetic presentation in IX except as the sort of quasi-omniscient 'beyond' occupied by its scription-factor. (This latter view might be considered god-like or 'theological', establishing a view that pertains to the angel, but the scription-factor of the text slips between a sort of third-person omniscient narrator and associating the narrative position

with the wreckage, ‘appears before *us*’, ‘what *we* call’).

*Des tours de progrès*¹¹⁵

Let reprise what this attempt at reading fragment IX has shown. First, when taken in isolation, the text enters into rhetorical relationship with Klee’s *Angelus Novus*. If read grammatically, then Thesis IX is a description of Klee’s *Angelus Novus*, which in turn presents a figure that resembles the angel of history. In contrast, a figural reading sees this move as establishing a textual image of the angel of history, in which *Angelus Novus* is entirely subsumed into a ‘single Benjaminian structure’, as Bahti argues. However, de Man’s conception of rhetoric suggests either be cannot definitively privileged. This, to an extent, plays out with an allegorical structure that alternates between theological and profane, and sets them antithetically against each other, to the detriment of those who would measure themselves against the infinite. On the side of the profane, we have the actual existence of the Klee painting in the world, and the ‘chain of events before *us*’; for the theological, the angel, the angel’s view, and the storm blowing from paradise.

The second half of the passage has been mentioned as context or co-text but subjected to as yet little rhetorical analysis. These last sentences in IX are, of course, of great rhetorical importance. ‘But a storm is blowing from Paradise and has got caught in his wings [...] This storm drives him irresistibly into the future, to which his back is turned, while the pile of debris before him grows toward the sky. What we call progress is *this* storm [original italics, *ist diese Sturm*]’.¹¹⁶ As already noted, this storm is presented as more powerful than the angel – who is already massive. The angel would like to [*möchte/voudrait*] to ‘awaken the dead and

make whole what has been smashed' but it is unclear whether the angel would have the power to do so without the storm, to bring about 'Judgement Day' and make all of history citable (cf. III).¹¹⁷ However, what is clear is that this last line is a rhetorical turn, akin to the *volta* of a Shakespearian or Petrarchan sonnet.¹¹⁸ The allegorical structure of the passage sets up what appears to be a dialectical relationship between theological and profane, but this last line certainly does not resolve the tension.

Akin to de Man's reading of Yeats, this line presents a sort of rhetorical undecidability that complicates an already complex thematic development. The progression of sublime excess of might in the allegorical narration presents this storm as that which has *dominion* over the textual scene, and over all of history. The storm 'we call progress' could be read as a sort of monadological shock, 'by which thinking is crystalized as a monad'. Having given the storm theological might, 'blowing from Paradise', and more power than the angel of history at, this line shocks precisely because it relates the storm to the multiple critiques of 'progress' in the co-text, on 'our' level. In VIII 'fascism has a chance' because 'in the name of progress, its opponents treat it as a historical norm', in X 'politicians' stubborn faith in progress', XI, 'only the progress in mastering nature, not the retrogression of society', XIII 'the concept of mankind's historical progress cannot be sundered from the concept of its progression through homogeneous empty time';¹¹⁹ only the latter seems to make reference to something beyond the politically profane. Indeed, this 'empty time' could be an analogue for the storm in IX.

As a consequence, akin to Yeats, the view of the *dominion* of the storm is called into question; its scale as greater than the scope of the angel which is almost too large for presentation becomes problematic. If 'we call' it progress then this puts it on a human, profane level rather something beyond the angel, or at the very least if 'we call' it then it has

Textual Practice

a manifestation at ‘our’ level, at the level of the human and profane. Kant says of the dynamic sublime that when safe at home a great storm ‘gives us the courage to measure ourselves against the apparent all-powerfulness of nature’.¹²⁰ However, since the text places the reader both within the wreckage and as a viewer of the painting/textual image, we are denied this comfort of exclusion. In de Man’s discussion of the disagreements between Kant and Schiller on the sublime, he argues that where Kant sees only an epistemological problem, Schiller only a psychological situation.¹²¹ However, while this line potentially inverts the allegorical play between theological and profane, it also combines the epistemological problem, attempting present messianic universal history (or now-time as a fragment of messianic time) – the angel’s vision, with the genuine danger faced by the historical subject as part of the ever growing pile of wreckage.

An interpretative gloss might attempt to resolve this tension; however, a more rhetorical focus merely tries to understand what resistances this produces to interpretation. (Weigel, for example, rightly insists on the dynamism of the image-construct). This rhetorical reading shows how the shifting perspectives maintain the *dynamis* in the face of attempts to pin down meaning. There is a similar problem with attributing reference to ‘we’ – as with the chain metaphor. Is this an inclusive ‘we’, all of humanity, including ‘the historical materialist’? Or, is it an excluding ‘we’, and if so, who would it exclude? This ‘we’ seems to include the narrative voice of OCH in many of the other fragments. The ‘this is what *we call*’ [my italics], however, as well as suggesting something profane still allows for the possibility of this being *doxa* or appearance to the essence of the storm (‘in reality’). Rather than confirm a duality of interpretations, one grammatical and one figural, as does de Man’s reading of Yeats’s ‘How can we know the dancer from the dance?’; we are presented with a yet greater fragmentation of rhetorical possibilities. Grammatical readings of the first lines lead to Klee’s

Angelus Novus, a picture that exists in the world, and that this complicates the rhetorical schema by inducing another act of reading from the spectator who has to decide in what sense and at what scale the painting is to be taken. The painting, however, still works as part of the allegorical schema oscillating between theological and sacred. Grammatical reading sends the spectator the view of the angel of history through the profane image of a painting, ‘Thou shalt not make a graven image’ (the sublime), and then the figural or metaphorical image that then appears – Benjamin interpreting Klee interpreting the angel and, as Bahti notes, Scholem interpreting Klee (the latter two the inverse of what Jakobson calls ‘intersemiotic translation or *transmutation*).¹²² In Bahti’s more figural account (and both Löwy’s and Weigel’s) the painting is subsumed by the description and the tableau is accessed, oddly, more directly, without the complicating displacement of Klee’s angel; in Weigel’s account three separate angels (Scholem’s is eloquent, Klee’s, and the mute angel of history) stand in contrast to each other – a largely figural reading. The last line, with its ambiguous relation of profane to theological or messianic, complicates this schema further. Is the storm the illusion of modern progress, as seen elsewhere in OCH? Or does it remain theological in scale, but we, from our limited perspective, merely *call* it progress as the angel ‘progresses’ backwards into the future, into empty time? While there seems to be a separation between the debris, storm and angel, this would suggest that there is some room for human agency, however small – even on a theological scale. *Angelus Novus* as the material-profane counterpart to the messianic also functions metonymically with this *volta* – the background of the picture would be the storm.

Conclusion: this is what *we call* allegory

de Man says in his essay on Pascal in *Aesthetic Ideology*, ‘The (ironic) pseudo-knowledge of this impossibility, which pretends to order sequentially, in a narrative, what is actually the

Textual Practice

destruction of all sequence, is what we call allegory.’¹²³ In the case of OCH this ironic pseudo-knowledge is played out through a complex rhetorical (in de Man’s sense) structure that destroys narrative certainty, the ‘logical’ sequence of progression. Warminski further clarifies this gesture of de Man’s:

[I]n the case of *what we call* ideology, *what we call* the figural dimension of language, *what we call* text, and, we might add, *what we call* language—if we ask what these allegories are allegories *of*, the most ‘direct’ answer would have to be that they are allegories *of* reference, which amounts to the same thing as saying that they are all ‘allegories *of* of,’ since ‘of’ is the very bearer of the referential function, the ‘carrying-back’ function, ‘itself.’¹²⁴

The referential function in OCH returns grammar to rhetoric and rhetoric to grammar. This indeed is what we might ‘call’ allegory. The structures of grammar and rhetoric identified here are all allegories *of*, allegories of reference, allegories of the (im)possibility of representing universal (messianic) history, linked to a ‘carrying back’ that is always already recursive. The ‘emphatic clarity’ of IX does not stand in the service of something that may be represented, rather it is an ironic allegorical void ‘that signifies precisely the non-being of what it represents’.¹²⁵

In the exegetical history of the text it seems that critics have predominantly privileged either grammar over rhetoric or figure over grammar; however, it is the tensions and conflicts between multiple interpretations, and the images that they either engender or interpret (‘harmonious even in their contrast’ as Kant says of the sublime¹²⁶) that produce a sublime feeling. What is presented in the ninth thesis – the angel’s view of the entirety of history as the maintenance of a simultaneity, exceeds the presentation to the extent that it is smashed to pieces (*Trümmer*) – but the material supplementarity of *Angelus Novus* within the text forces

the reader to continually question and remain open to the presented of the presentation. It is the excess of differing scales as recursive¹²⁷ – which oscillate between grammar and rhetoric – that calls into question the notion of representation. There may indeed be both grammatization of rhetoric – the metonymic relation between the discrete metaphorical devices –, and rhetorization of grammar – for example ‘this is how the angel of history must look’, which is generally read in the same sense as a rhetorical question, but its literality is not excluded. There is an irreconcilable conflict between the colossal figure of the angel of history and a Klee painting named *Angelus Novus*. Benjamin’s text dislocates the figure from ‘reality’, calling into question the ontological possibility of representation, of presenting the past ‘the way it really was’ and so of presenting history, culture, and art the way it *really* is; this is what we *call* allegory – a meta-rhetorical destruction of sequence, of chains. It is this effect that prevents the ninth thesis from being a ‘modern’ sublime in Lyotard’s parlance; it prevents ‘the consensus of a taste that would make it possible to share collectively nostalgia for the unattainable’ through this allegorical fragmentation.¹²⁸ Instead through the form of Klee’s *Angelus Novus* the ‘form of the injunction’ is stretched toward the infinite, only apprehensible; the unrepresentability of what is presented makes the new angel of history therein a dizzying excess of scales, confounding aesthetic *comprehension* at a mere 31.8 x 24.2 centimetres combined with twelve lines of text. This aesthetico-rhetorical play, this allegory, demonstrates, performs the impossibility of historiographical practice as anything but delusional nostalgia, it performs the necessity of trying to write a different kind of history, it demonstrates the possibility of inducing a moment of danger for the naïve model of inevitable progress held by the social democrats – and which continues to be held across the political spectrum in our present.

¹ Paul De Man, *Allegories of Reading: Figural Language in Rousseau, Nietzsche, Rilke, and Proust* (New Haven, Conn.: Yale Univ. Press, 1979), 226.

² Paul De Man, *The Resistance to Theory* (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 1986), 73–105.

³ De Man, *Allegories of Reading*, 9.

⁴ I say ‘largely’ as de Man did provide a number of comments on Benjamin’s theory of history and Derrida also makes passing references in the notes to *Specters of Marx*, (NY: Routledge, 2006) among other works. See Robert Savino Oventile, ‘Paul de Man Now, Or, Nihilism in the Right Company’. *Symploke* 21, no. 1 (2013): 325–39; and Jill Petersen Adams, ‘Mourning, The Messianic, and The Specter: Derrida’s Appropriation of Benjamin in Specters of Marx’. *Philosophy Today* 5 (2007): 140–47. Derrida also mentions ‘the straight gate through which the messiah might enter’ towards the end of *Archive Fever*, (Chicago: Chicago UP, 1996).

⁵ Marc De Wilde, ‘Benjamin’s Politics of Remembrance: A Reading of “Über Den Begriff Der Geschichte”’, in *A Companion to the Works of Walter Benjamin*, ed. Rolf J. Goebel, Studies in German Literature, Linguistics, and Culture (Rochester, NY: Camden House, 2009). See also Kia Lindroos, *Now-Time Image-Space: Temporalization of Politics in Walter Benjamin’s Philosophy of History and Art*, (Jyväskylä, Finland: University of Jyväskylä, 1998), 80–83.

⁶ Michael Löwy, *Fire Alarm: Reading Walter Benjamin’s On the Concept of History*, trans. Chris Turner (London ; New York: Verso, 2005).

⁷ Stéphane Symons, *Walter Benjamin: Presence of Mind, Failure to Comprehend* (Leiden: Brill, 2013), 15.

⁸ Angela B. Moorjani, *The Aesthetics of Loss and Lessness* (NY: St. Martin’s Press, 1992). Suzanne Hobson, *Angels of Modernism: Religion, Culture, Aesthetics 1910-1960*. (Palgrave Macmillan, 2014). Michael Serres, *Angels, a Modern Myth* (Random House, 1995). Paul Colilli, *The Angel’s Corpse*, (NY: St. Martin’s Press, 1999).

⁹ Timothy Bahti, ‘History as Rhetorical Enactment: Walter Benjamin’s Theses On the Concept of History’, *Diacritics*. 9, no. 3 (1979): 5.

¹⁰ Sigrid Weigel, *Body-and Image-Space: Re-Reading Walter Benjamin*, Warwick Studies in European Philosophy (London: Routledge, 1996), 51–56.

¹¹ Alison Ross, *Walter Benjamin’s Concept of the Image* (London: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group, 2015), 110.

¹² Beatrice Hanssen, ‘Portrait of Melancholy (Benjamin, Warburg, Panofsky)’, *Mln* 114, no. 5 (1999): 991–1013; Susan Handelman, ‘Walter Benjamin and the Angel of History’, *CrossCurrents*, 1991, 344–52; Max Pensky, *Melancholy Dialectics: Walter Benjamin and the Play of Mourning* (Univ of Massachusetts Press, 2001); Chun-yen Chen, ‘Foreword: Wings of Patience’, *Concentric: Literary and Cultural Studies* 37, no. 2 (2011): 3–6.

¹³ Handelman, ‘Walter Benjamin and the Angel of History’, 346.

¹⁴ Philippe Fleury, ‘L’Ange comme figure messianique dans la philosophie de l’histoire de Walter Benjamin / The Angel as a Messianic figure in Walter Benjamin’s Philosophy of History’, *Archives de sciences sociales des religions* 78, no. 1 (1992): 169–77.

¹⁵ D. Robert DeChaine does, however, note the potential importance of Benjamin’s thought for the study of rhetoric, without analysing Benjamin’s rhetoric at any length. D. Robert DeChaine, ‘Magic, Mimesis, and Revolutionary Praxis: Illuminating Walter Benjamin’s Rhetoric of Redemption’, *Western Journal of Communication (Includes Communication Reports)* 64, no. 3 (2000): 285–307.

¹⁶ Robert S. Lehman, ‘Allegories of Rending: Killing Time with Walter Benjamin’, *New Literary History* 39, no. 2 (2008): 233–50; Bainard Cowan, ‘Walter Benjamin’s Theory of Allegory’, *New German Critique*, no. 22 (1981): 109–22.

- ¹⁷ Ackbar Abbas, 'On Fascination: Walter Benjamin's Images', *New German Critique*, no. 48 (1989): 43–62; Irving Wohlfarth, 'Darko Suvin, 'The Arrested Moment in Benjamin's "Theses": Epistemology vs. Politics, Image vs. Story', *Neohelicon* 28, no. 1 (2001): 177–94. Walter Benjamin's Image of Interpretation', *New German Critique*, no. 17 (1979): 70–98.
- ¹⁸ Esther Leslie, *Walter Benjamin: Overpowering Conformism*, Modern European Thinkers (London: Pluto Press, 2000).
- ¹⁹ To give Löwy proper credit, however, it should be noted that he does identify Thesis IX as 'This thesis sums up, "as though in a focal point", the whole of the document', *Fire Alarm*, 62.
- ²⁰ Rodolphe Gasché, 'Reading Chiasms: An Introduction', in Andrzej Warminski, *Readings in Interpretation: Hölderlin, Hegel, Heidegger*, by (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 1987), xv.
- ²¹ Roland Barthes, *S/Z*, trans. Richard Miller (Oxford: Blackwell, 1990).
- ²² Löwy, *Fire Alarm*, 62.
- ²³ Herman Rapaport, 'Benjamin as Historian', *Clio* 36, no. 3 (2007): 405,407.
- ²⁴ Weigel also does so, but via an analysis that identifies three separate angels, Scholem's, Klee's, and the angel of history. Weigel, *Body-and Image-Space*, 52–53.
- ²⁵ Löwy, *Fire Alarm*, 62.
- ²⁶ Jacques Derrida, 'Signature Event Context', in *Margins of Philosophy*, trans. Alan Bass (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1982), 307–30.
- ²⁷ George Lakoff and Mark Johnson, *Metaphors We Live By* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2003); Michael Reddy, 'The Conduit Metaphor', *Metaphor and Thought* 2 (1979): 285–324.
- ²⁸ Walter Benjamin, *Selected Writings*, ed. Michael William Jennings and Howard Eiland, vol. 4: 1938-1940, *Selected Writings*, Walter Benjamin. Michael W. Jennings, general ed.; 4 (Cambridge, MA: Belknap Press, 2003), 392.
- ²⁹ Rapaport, 'Benjamin as Historian', 393.
- ³⁰ Ross, *Walter Benjamin's Concept of the Image*, 111–14.
- ³¹ Ross, 114.
- ³² Gershom Scholem, 'Walter Benjamin and His Angel', *On Jews and Judaism in Crisis: Selected Essays*, 1976, 198–236.
- ³³ Paul De Man, *The Resistance to Theory*, ed. Wlad Godzich, (Minneapolis: Univ. of Minnesota Press, 1997), 88.
- ³⁴ Andrzej Warminski, *Readings in Interpretation: Hölderlin, Hegel, Heidegger* (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 1987), 150. See also, Gasché, 'Reading Chiasms', p. xv.
- ³⁵ Gasché, 'Reading Chiasms', p. xv.
- ³⁶ Gasché, 'Reading Chiasms', p. xiv; Jacques Derrida, 'Des Tours de Babel', in *Psyche: Inventions of the Other* (Stanford: Stanford UP, 2007), 206.
- ³⁷ Evidently, it would be possible to repeat the analysis that follows using Derrida's conception of metaphor as catachresis from 'White Mythology' to a similar end.
- ³⁸ See, for example, Robert S. Lehman, 'Allegories of Rending: Killing Time with Walter Benjamin', *New Literary History* 39, no. 2 (2008): 233–50.
- ³⁹ Paul De Man, *Blindness and Insight: Essays in the Rhetoric of Contemporary Criticism* (London: Routledge, 2005), 173.
- ⁴⁰ Cf. Walter Benjamin, *Ecrits français*, Collection Folio Essais 418 (Paris: Gallimard, 2003), 438. The French version includes a variation here: '*panser les blessures*', heal (the) wounds. Interestingly, the *Écrits* version does not include the citation from the Scholem poem.
- ⁴¹ Benjamin, *Selected Writings*, 4: 1938-1940:392. In German: Es gibt ein Bild von Klee, das Angelus Novus heißt. Ein Engel ist darauf dargestellt, der aussieht, als wäre er im Begriff, sich von etwas zu entfernen, worauf er starrt. Seine Augen sind aufgerissen, sein Mund steht offen und seine Flügel sind ausgespannt. Der Engel der Geschichte muß so aussehen. Er hat das Antlitz der Vergangenheit zugewendet. Wo eine Kette von Begebenheiten vor *uns* erscheint, da sieht er eine einzige Katastrophe, die unablässig Trümmer auf Trümmer häuft und sie ihm vor die Füße schleudert. Er mochte wohl verweilen, die Toten wecken und das Zerschlagene zusammenflügen. Aber ein Sturm weht vom Paradiese her, der sich in seinen Flügeln verfangen hat und so stark ist, daß der Engel sie nicht mehr schließen kann. Dieser Sturm treibt ihn unaufhaltsam in die Zukunft, der er den Rücken kehrt, während der Trümmerhaufen vor ihm zum Himmel wächst. Das, was wir den Fortschritt nennen, ist *dieser* Sturm. Benjamin's French 'translation' written around the same time as the German, whilst in Paris, can be found in *Ecrits français*, 438; oddly, it is rarely mentioned and even less cited.
- ⁴² Lehman, 'Allegories of Rending: Killing Time with Walter Benjamin', 233.
- ⁴³ Kia Lindroos, *Now-Time Image-Space: Temporalization of Politics in Walter Benjamin's Philosophy of History and Art*, SoPhi (Jyväskylä, Finland: University of Jyväskylä, 1998), 80–81; Jacques Derrida, *On the Name*, Meridian: Crossing Aesthetics (Stanford, Calif: Stanford University Press, 1995) Derrida is very suspicious of didactic metaphor. ; See also Alexander Hope, 'Khōra – plus de Métaphore', *Textual Practice* 29,

no. 4 (7 June 2015): 611–30, <https://doi.org/10.1080/0950236X.2014.936486>.

⁴⁴ Derrida, 'Des Tours de Babel', 223.

⁴⁵ Derrida, 206.

⁴⁶ cf. Michael Löwy, 'Benjamin (Walter) *Ecrits français*', *Archives de Sciences Sociales des Religions* 76, no. 1 (1991): 220–21; Benjamin, *Ecrits français*.

⁴⁷ De Man, *The Resistance to Theory*, 73.

⁴⁸ cf. Timothy Bahti, 'History as Rhetorical Enactment: Walter Benjamin's Theses On the Concept of History', *Diacritics*. 9, no. 3 (1979): 2–17. Many commentators have queried the Zohn translation published in *Illuminations*.

⁴⁹ Derrida, 'Des Tours de Babel', 205,225.

⁵⁰ Jean-François Lyotard, 'Answering the Question: What Is Postmodernism?', in *The Postmodern Condition: A Report on Knowledge*, trans. Régis Durand (Manchester University Press, 1984), 71–82.

⁵¹ 'Sur-vival (*survie*)' is Derrida's play on Benjamin's '*Fortleben*', indicating the overlap of the translation and original, continuing to live on.

⁵² Roman Jakobson, 'On Linguistic Aspects of Translation', in *The Translation Studies Reader*, ed. Lawrence Venuti (London: Routledge, 2012), 127; Derrida, 'Des Tours de Babel', 198.

⁵³ Derrida, 'Des Tours de Babel', 222–23.

⁵⁴ Walter Benjamin, 'Theses on the Philosophy of History', in *Illuminations*, ed. Hannah Arendt, trans. Harry Zohn (New York: Schocken Books, 1986), 253–64.

⁵⁵ Derrida, 'Des Tours de Babel', 211.

⁵⁶ Paul De Man, 'Semiology and Rhetoric', in *Allegories of Reading: Figural Language in Rousseau, Nietzsche, Rilke, and Proust* (New Haven: Yale UP, 1979), 3–19.

⁵⁷ Walter Benjamin, *Gesammelte Schriften: Autobiographische Schriften*, Suhrkamp-Taschenbuch Wissenschaft, Bd. 936 (Frankfurt/M: Suhrkamp, 1991), 697.

⁵⁸ Weigel, *Body-and Image-Space*, 52.

⁵⁹ Timothy Bahti, 'History as Rhetorical Enactment: Walter Benjamin's Theses On the Concept of History', *Diacritics*. 9, no. 3 (1979): 7.

⁶⁰ Bahti, 7.

⁶¹ Weigel, *Body-and Image-Space*.

⁶² Bahti, 6-7. Clearly, as a reader of Derrida, Bahti's choice of 'verbal' is somewhat disconcerting, hence my preference for a 'textual image' in this instance.

⁶³ Bahti, 7.

⁶⁴ De Man, 'Semiology and Rhetoric', 9.

⁶⁵ De Man, *Allegories of Reading*, 9.

⁶⁶ De Man, 'Semiology and Rhetoric', 9.

⁶⁷ Löwy, *Fire Alarm*, 63.

⁶⁸ Geoffrey Hartman, 'Benjamin in Hope', *Critical Inquiry* 25, no. 2 (1999): 346.

⁶⁹ Weigel, *Body-and Image-Space*, 52–53. While I would query Weigel's classical understanding of metaphor, she does show far more attentiveness to the figural problematic of the fragment than the vast majority of commentators. Cf. Derrida, 'Des Tours de Babel', 210–11.

⁷⁰ 'On the Concept of History', in *Working with Walter Benjamin*, by Andrew Benjamin, Recovering a Political Philosophy (Edinburgh University Press, 2013), 162; Weigel, *Body-and Image-Space*, 52.

⁷¹ Lindsay Waters and Wlad Godzich, eds., *Reading de Man Reading* (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 1989), 9.

⁷² Löwy, *Fire Alarm*, 63.

⁷³ Cf. Derrida, 'Des Tours de Babel', 223. Derrida, following Benjamin, proposes translation as a form of experience, as the translation of experience.

⁷⁴ Bainard Cowan, 'Walter Benjamin's Theory of Allegory', *New German Critique*, no. 22 (1981): 112–13.

⁷⁵ De Man, *Blindness and Insight*, 35.

⁷⁶ De Man, *Allegories of Reading*, 205.

⁷⁷ Jacques Derrida, 'White Mythology: Metaphor in the Text of Philosophy', in *Margins of Philosophy*, trans. Alan Bass (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1982), 207–71.

⁷⁸ Robert Savino Oventile, 'Paul de Man Now, or, Nihilism in the Right Company', *Symploke* 21, no. 1 (2013): 325–39.

⁷⁹ Paul De Man, *Aesthetic Ideology*, ed. Andrzej Warminski (Minneapolis: Univ. of Minnesota Press, 2008), 61.

⁸⁰ Benjamin, *Selected Writings*, 4: 1938-1940:391.

⁸¹ Benjamin, *Ecrits français*, 438.

⁸² Löwy, *Fire Alarm*, 61.

⁸³ De Man, 'Semiology and Rhetoric', 14.

⁸⁴ Benjamin, *Gesammelte Schriften*, 697.

- ⁸⁵ Weigel, *Body-and Image-Space*, 54.
- ⁸⁶ Benjamin, *Selected Writings*, 4: 1938-1940:390.
- ⁸⁷ Benjamin, 4: 1938-1940:397.
- ⁸⁸ Bahti, 'History as Rhetorical Enactment: Walter Benjamin's Theses On the Concept of History', 6 'does this text end?' .
- ⁸⁹ Benjamin, *Selected Writings*, 4: 1938-1940:405.
- ⁹⁰ Benjamin, 4: 1938-1940:391–92.
- ⁹¹ Immanuel Kant, *Critique of the Power of Judgment*, trans. Paul Guyer (Cambridge, UK; New York: Cambridge University Press, 2000), 128.
- ⁹² Kant, 135.
- ⁹³ Bahti, 'History as Rhetorical Enactment: Walter Benjamin's Theses On the Concept of History', 7.
- ⁹⁴ A reviewer of an earlier version of this paper suggested the angel could be like the Hubble telescope, a camera that views a great area; however, while this article demonstrates a great deal of plurality in the potential interpretation of this fragment, this could not be one of them – for the reason already given: the angel requires an elevated viewpoint but has the wreckage of history at his feet, or in front of him (see Fr. Below). Werckmeister, 'Walter Benjamin's Angel of History', 261, also suggests an angel "high in the sky", and an association with cameras, but a high-flying angel is at odds with the preposition *vor* as "in front of" or "before", in which Zohn's translation is probably more accurate than the "at" given in the *Selected Writings; Illuminations* (NY: Schocken Books, 1986), 257; *Selected Writings*, 392. Benjamin's French gives '*tandis les décombres, en face de lui, montent au ciel*'; 'while the debris, in front of him, rises towards the sky' (my trans.).
- ⁹⁵ Cowan, 'Walter Benjamin's Theory of Allegory', 114.
- ⁹⁶ Cowan, 114.
- ⁹⁷ Jacques Derrida, *The Truth in Painting*, trans. Bennington, Geoff and McLeod, Ian (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1987), 125.
- ⁹⁸ Michel de Certeau, 'Writings and Histories', in *The Writing of History*, trans. Tom Conley (New York: Columbia Univ. Press, 1992), 1–16.
- ⁹⁹ Clearly, an investigation of the relationship between OCH and de Certeau's on writing history could be productive; however, it lies outside the scope of this article.
- ¹⁰⁰ Derrida, *The Truth in Painting*, 125.
- ¹⁰¹ Derrida, *The Truth in Painting*, 125.
- ¹⁰² Derrida, *The Truth in Painting*, 125.
- ¹⁰³ Kant in Derrida, *The Truth in Painting*, 125.
- ¹⁰⁴ Benjamin, *Selected Writings*, 391.
- ¹⁰⁵ Derrida, *The Truth in Painting*, 133.
- ¹⁰⁶ Cf. De Man, *Aesthetic Ideology*, 125.
- ¹⁰⁷ Benjamin, *Selected Writings*, 396.
- ¹⁰⁸ Jacques Derrida, *The Truth in Painting*, trans. Bennington, Geoff and McLeod, Ian (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1987), 126.
- ¹⁰⁹ Benjamin, *Selected Writings*, 396.
- ¹¹⁰ Peter D. Fenves, *The Messianic Reduction: Walter Benjamin and the Shape of Time*, Meridian, Crossing Aesthetics (Stanford, Calif: Stanford University Press, 2011), 243.
- ¹¹¹ Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz and Lloyd Strickland, *Leibniz's Monadology: A New Translation and Guide* (Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2014), 128–30.
- ¹¹² Benjamin, *Selected Writings*, 391-395.
- ¹¹³ See for example the essays by Werner Hamacher, Robert Gibbs and Howard Caygill in Andrew E. Benjamin, ed., *Walter Benjamin and History*, Walter Benjamin Studies Series (London ; New York: Continuum, 2005); Eric Jacobson, 'Locating the Messianic: In Search of Causation and Benjamin's Last Message', *Journal for Cultural Research* 13, no. 3–4 (2009): 207–23; Fabrizio Desideri, 'Intermittency: The Differential of Time and the Integral of Space. The Intensive Spatiality of the Monad, the Apokatastasis and the Messianic World in Benjamin's Latest Thinking', *Aisthesis. Pratiche, Linguaggi e Saperi Dell'estetico* 9, no. 1 (2016): 177–87.
- ¹¹⁴ Kant, *Critique of the Power of Judgment*, 108; emphasis original.
- ¹¹⁵ This is a pun on Derrida's title '*Des tours de Babel*', in which '*tour*' is both tower and turn, in the sense of a rhetorical turn.
- ¹¹⁶ Benjamin, *Selected Writings*, 4: 1938-1940:392.
- ¹¹⁷ Benjamin, 4: 1938-1940:390.
- ¹¹⁸ Intriguingly, this kind of 'volta' has been suggested to be typical of de Man's own thought. Cf. Ortwin de Graef, *Titanic Light: Paul de Man's Post-Romanticism, 1960-1969*, Texts and Contexts, v. 13 (Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press, 1995), 80.
- ¹¹⁹ Benjamin, *Selected Writings*, 4: 1938-1940:392–95.
- ¹²⁰ Kant, *Critique of the Power of Judgment*, 145.

¹²¹ De Man, *Aesthetic Ideology*, 143–45.

¹²² Jakobson, 'On Linguistic Aspects of Translation', 127.

¹²³ De Man, *Aesthetic Ideology*, 69.

¹²⁴ Warminski in De Man, 18–19.

¹²⁵ De Man, *Blindness and Insight*, 35.

¹²⁶ Kant, *Critique of the Power of Judgment*, 142.

¹²⁷ Douglas R. Hofstadter, *Gödel, Escher, Bach: An Eternal Golden Braid*, 20th anniversary ed (New York: Basic Books, 1999), chap. 5.

¹²⁸ Lyotard, 'Answering the Question: What Is Postmodernism?', 81.